

Synthesis and Mass Spectral Studies of Some New 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles

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Some new 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been synthesized in good yields from the reaction of aldehyde semicarbazones with bromine in presence of acetic acid and sodium acetate. The reaction proceeds through the formation of nitrilimine intermediate which on cyclization affords the corresponding 1,3,4-oxadiazoles. The structures of the oxadiazoles were confirmed on the basis of spectral studies with special emphasis on mass spectral studies of five oxadiazoles.

WE earlier reported the syntheses of 1,4-dihydro-1,2,4,5-tetrazines through the use of arsonium¹ and pyridinium ylides²⁻⁴. In these reactions, the formation of nitrilimine intermediate takes place and the latter dimerizes to yield the corresponding 1,4-dihydro-1,2,4,5-tetrazines¹. Gibson⁵ reported the synthesis of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles from semicarbazones by the action of bromine in the presence of glacial acetic acid and sodium acetate. This reaction also proceeds through the intermediacy of nitrilimine. We have extended this reaction to the synthesis of some new 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and studied the detailed mass fragmentation of five representative compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on an electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer 577 Grating ir spectrophotometer in KBr pellet. PMR spectra were scanned on Perkin-Elmer RB 12 spectrometer in CD₃OD using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were taken on MC-30 Mass spectrometer with direct inlet system. All the aldehydes used were purified either by distillation or by recrystallization. Anhydrous sodium acetate of AR grade was used in all the reaction.

Preparation of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles: To a suspension of an appropriate aldehyde semicarbazone (1.5 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (3.2 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), was added bromine (0.6 ml in 2 ml of glacial acetic acid) with stirring. The mixture warmed up and turned into clear solution. After 15 min the mixture was poured into water (25 ml) and the precipitated solid was collected, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to give the corresponding 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole as needles or prisms.

The melting points, yields and elemental analysis of all the 1,3,4-oxadiazoles synthesized by this method are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Aldehyde semicarbazones (Ia-h) reacted with bromine in glacial acetic acid containing anhydrous sodium acetate, to give the corresponding 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (IIa-h) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

It has been reported⁶ earlier that the aldehyde semicarbazone reacts with bromine to give semicarbazone bromide, which in the presence of sodium acetate undergoes dehydrobromination to furnish the reactive nitrilimine intermediate. The latter changes into the corresponding 1,3,4-oxadiazole (II) by 1,5-dipolar cycloaddition.

In ir spectrum, the oxadiazole ring has been characterized primarily by the bands at about 970 cm⁻¹^{6,7}, 1020-1035 cm⁻¹⁷ due to C-O-C linkage and at 1620-1645 cm⁻¹^{8,9} corresponding to the C=N stretching frequencies. All the compounds exhibited the characteristic absorption bands in these two regions. Besides this, a doublet in the region 3100-3450 cm⁻¹ corresponded to the symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of NH₂ group^{6,10}. In pmr spectra, a multiplet in the region δ 6.1-7.2 ppm was observed due to aromatic protons. The methyl and methoxy protons appeared as singlets at δ 1.8 and 3.0-3.25 ppm respectively. The amino protons could not be observed in pmr spectra. However, the presence of amino group was unambiguously confirmed by ir spectra.

Mass spectral studies of 1,3,4-oxadiazoles: The structure of the synthesized 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been confirmed unambiguously by mass spectral studies. The mass spectral studies of a few 1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been reported¹¹⁻¹⁸ and our results are in close conformity with these results.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF 2-AMINO-5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLINE

Product	X	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis : Found (Calcd.) (%)		
				C	H	N
IIa	H	242 ^A	85	59.08 (59.63)	4.30 (4.35)	26.00 (26.09)
IIb	4-OCH ₃	248 ^B	80	55.91 (56.54)	4.65 (4.71)	21.88 (21.99)
IIc	4-Cl	274	87	48.46 (49.10)	3.01 (3.07)	21.32 (21.48)
IId	4-NO ₂	250	80	45.91 (46.60)	2.86 (2.91)	27.03 (27.18)
IIe	2,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃	255	75	52.07 (52.59)	5.15 (5.18)	16.61 (16.73)
IIf	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃	270	78	52.11 (52.59)	5.13 (5.18)	16.63 (16.73)
IIg	3-NO ₂	262	82	46.09 (46.60)	2.85 (2.91)	27.06 (27.18)
IIh	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	258	74	58.38 (58.82)	5.88 (5.88)	27.34 (27.45)

A, lit.⁶ m.p. 241-243°, B, lit.⁶ m.p. 248-249°

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IONS OBSERVED IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF THE COMPOUNDS 2a-e

Compound	Ion 1 (M ⁺) (m/e)	Ion 2 (m/e)	Ion 3 (m/e)	Ion 4 (m/e)	Ion 5 (m/e)	Ion 6 (m/e)	
IIa	161 (97%)	105 (67.5%)	77 (100%)	118 (73%)	91 (47%)	—	
IIb	191 (100%)	135 (99%)	107 (10%)	148 (31%)	—	120 (8%)	
IIc	195 (100%)	139 (76.5%)	111 (74%)	152 (95%)	125 (50%)	—	
IId	206 (100%)	150 (20%)	—	163 (98%)	—	135 (20%)	
IIe	Ion 7 (m/e) 251 (84%)	Ion 8 (m/e) 195 (39%)	Ion 9 (m/e) 178 (100%)	Ion 10 (m/e) 150 (22%)	Ion 11 (m/e) 165 (36%)	Ion 12 (m/e) 234 (18%)	Ion 13 (m/e) 206 (6%)

Note: The relative abundances of the ions are given in brackets. The relative abundance of the base peak has been arbitrarily taken as 100%.

The fragmentation of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives is initiated mainly by two schemes indicated by path 'A' and path 'B' in Scheme 2. The path 'A' involving the cleavage at the bonds O-C₂ and C₅-N₄ leads to the formation of the benzoyl ion 2. The path 'B' on the other hand involves the cleavage at O-C₂ and C₂-N₃ thereby giving the ion 4.

Our results indicate that while the mass spectral fragmentation of the compounds IIa-d follows a similar pattern, compound IIe fragments by a slightly different mechanism. Scheme 2 depicts the mass fragmentation of the compounds IIa-d while the Scheme 3 shows the mass fragmentation of the compound IIe.

The molecular ion usually forms the base peak except in the case of IIa and IIe. In the case of the former, the ion at m/e 77 forms the base peak while in the case of the latter, the base peak appears at m/e 178.

The relative abundances of the ions 2 and 4 (Table 2) indicate that the electronic nature of the substituent group in the phenyl ring affects the mode of initial fragmentation, i.e. path 'A' or path 'B'. In the case of IIb (X=4-MeO), ion 2b (m/e 135) is more intense (99%) but in the case of compounds

IIc (X=4-Cl) and IId (X=4-NO₂), the ions 4c (m/e 152, 95%) and 4d (m/e 163, 98%) respectively are formed preferentially. It shows that an electron-withdrawing substituent makes, as expected, the cleavage of O-C₂ bond comparatively more facile thereby making the path 'B' a preferential mode of fragmentation. The ion 2b on the other hand is greatly stabilized, as shown below, by resonance.

The ion 2 usually eliminates CO to form ion 3 which undergoes further fragmentation, as shown in Scheme 2, to give other important peaks in the spectrum. In the case of 2b, fragmentation may also occur at methoxy group accompanied by the loss of formaldehyde to give the benzoyl cation at m/e 105. It appears that in 2d, the loss of NO₂ precedes the loss of CO to give the ion at m/e 104. The latter then loses CO to give the ion at m/e 76.

The ion 4 undergoes further fragmentation accompanied by the loss of a nitrogen molecule. The resulting ion undergoes rearrangement with or without the abstraction of a hydrogen atom to form the ion 5 or the radical ion 6, respectively. In the

Scheme 2

case of IIb, a strong peak appears at m/e 133 also, which may be attributed to the process involving loss of CH_3 from the ion 4b. The ions 5 and 6 undergo further fragmentation leading to the formation of other important ions as shown in Scheme 2.

As pointed out earlier, the compound IIc fragments in a slightly different manner. The presence of three electron releasing methoxy groups in the phenyl ring makes O-C₅ bond quite resistant to cleavage and therefore path 'A' (Scheme 3) becomes the preferred mode of fragmentation. This leads to the formation of trimethoxybenzoyl cation 8 at m/e 195. As pointed out earlier, the peak at m/e 178 forms the base peak in the spectrum. It appears that this ion (m/e 178) results from the loss of hydroxide radical from ion 8. This process involves the migration of a hydrogen from *ortho*-methoxy group on to the carbonyl oxygen followed by the loss of hydroxide radical. The extensive delocalization of the ionic charge in 9 makes it quite stable and therefore, it forms the base peak in the spectrum. The ion 9 may lose CO to give the ion 10 at m/e 150. The ion 8 may also split off formaldehyde to give the ion 11 at m/e 165. It appears that a minor process involving the loss of a hydroxide radical from the parent ion 7 competes with the above described path 'A'. This process has been designated as path 'B' in Scheme 3. This also involves the migration of a hydrogen

Scheme 3

from *ortho*-methoxy group on to the carbonyl oxygen followed by the loss of hydroxide radical. The resulting ion 12 (m/e 234) splits off nitrogen molecule to form the ion 13 at m/e 206.

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